

Investigating the Impact of Airstrips on Deforestation in Indigenous Territories of the Brazilian Amazon

Kate A. Booth^{*1}, Jonathan J. Huck^{†1} and Polyanna da Conceição Bispo^{‡1}

¹ MCGIS, Department of Geography, School of Environment, Education and Development, University of Manchester, Oxford Road, Manchester M13 9PL, UK

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Summary

Change detection techniques have been carried out to identify creation dates of airstrips within Indigenous Territories across the Brazilian Amazon. The creation of airstrips increases accessibility for anthropogenic activities to more remote and pristine areas of the rainforest. Understanding the creation dates of these airstrips allows the analysis of their impact on surrounding deforestation rates and extents. Current results show that our method can be used to identify the year that these airstrips were created. This research will contribute to a deeper understanding of how infrastructure accelerates deforestation and forest degradation, helping to guide interventions that mitigate environmental impacts.

KEYWORDS: Change Detection; Remote Sensing; Spatial Analysis; PELT, Degradation

1. Introduction

This study explores the impact of airstrips on deforestation within Indigenous Territories (ITs) in the Brazilian Amazon (BA). Indigenous Territories are an important type of protected area in the Amazon, and airstrips are critical enablers of illegal deforestation activities in these regions. From the research carried out by da Silva et al. (2023), we understand that airstrips contribute to biodiversity loss and habitat fragmentation within the surrounding rainforest due to their connections with illegal deforestation activities such as mining. Despite their significance, the direct relationship between airstrip establishment and deforestation within ITs remains underexplored. This research aims to fill that gap, providing insights to support targeted monitoring and policy interventions.

The BA rainforest acts as a major carbon sink for our planet. However, this key process in sustaining the Earth's climate has been disrupted by decades of increasing illegal activities such as logging and mining (Booth et al., 2024). Research suggests that the Amazon rainforest is fast approaching a crucial tipping point (Flores et al., 2024). Alongside this, the interchanging of Brazilian governments has prevented the consistent application of environmental protection policies and practices within ITs and Protected Areas (PAs) (Booth et al., 2024). This inconsistency has allowed illegal activities to encroach across PA and IT boundaries, enabled by the illegal development of transportation systems such as logging tracks and airstrips.

This research therefore seeks to use change detection analysis to understand the impact that newly introduced airstrips have on rates of deforestation in ITs in the Amazon rainforest. The methods presented here provide a means to both understand the impact of airstrips and detect new ones as they are developed.

* kate.booth@postgrad.manchester.ac.uk

† jonathan.huck@manchester.ac.uk

‡ polyanna.bispo@manchester.ac.uk

2. Methods

We have sourced point data determining the location of known airstrips (**Figure 1**) within Indigenous Territories of the Brazilian Amazon rainforest from MapBiomias (Mapbiomas.org, 2023). Airstrips are typically ~300-400 m in length and ~8-12 m wide (with a clearing ~30 m wide). Given the need for a long time series (to detect the time at which airstrips were first cleared) and moderate resolution (to capture cleared areas of ~3-4,000 m²), 30 m satellite imagery from Landsat was used as the basis for change detection. Though higher resolution products are available, they do not have the necessary temporal range for this study.

Figure 1 Example airstrip shown with length and width measurements and MapBiomias location point feature.

Normalised Vegetation Index (NDVI) were calculated from the Landsat imagery to aid the change detection process. We applied two change detection techniques that helped to pinpoint the moments within the time series that denoted changes in vegetation density. First, we used K-Means clustering to define clusters of similar NDVI values that could then support the subsequent application of the Pruned Exact Linear Time (PELT) approach to identify substantial reductions in vegetation that likely signal the creation of airstrip. The PELT technique is an exact algorithm with a linear time complexity, it works efficiently by eliminating unlikely change points to increase the speed of the process. Once these change detection points were highlighted, we then validated the technique using visual comparison of the corresponding Landsat imagery for a random subset of the images.

Once the year of creation of the airstrip has been identified, the rate and extent of deforestation in the surrounding areas can be analysed. We will conduct statistical testing to test our hypotheses:

- H_0 : There is no effect on the creation of airstrips on the surrounding levels of deforestation.
- H_1 : The creation of an airstrip results in an increase in rate and extent of deforestation within

the surrounding area.

Findings will be analysed for both spatial patterns (e.g., using LISA analysis – Anselin, 1995) and temporal patterns (e.g., relating the influx of airstrips to political shifts - Booth, 2024), in order to gain a greater understanding of the role of airstrips in the dynamics of illegal deforestation in Indigenous Territories in the Brazilian Amazon.

3. Results

Our results show that the airstrip creation year can be determined through PELT and K-Means clustering. **Figure 2** displays a ‘point of change occurring’ between the years 2010 – 2012, suggesting the period in which clearance took place for an airstrip (ID:508) in the MapBiomass dataset. NDVI values can be clearly seen to decrease from approximately 0.45 before the change point (red dashed line) to 0.29 afterwards, suggesting a substantial decrease in vegetation coverage commensurate with clearance for an airstrip.

Figure 2 NDVI time series for airstrip point ID: 508 with PELT and K-Means clustering applied.

An illustration of the ‘before’ (2010) and ‘after’ (2014) NDVI surface for the location of the same airstrip (ID:508) can be seen in **Figures 3a** and **3b** respectively. Though the difference is subtle (the airstrip is highlighted in **Figure 3b**) it is sufficient for detection using the proposed method.

This illustrative example demonstrates how the proposed method can be used to automatically detect the creation data of known airstrip locations in Indigenous Territories in the Brazilian Amazon Rainforest. Having the ability to efficiently identify these creation points allows for us to then analyse and monitor the impacts this has on the surrounding deforestation and degradation. This work is near completion, and an oral presentation will comprise an overview of the method followed by a detailed analysis of the complex spatio-temporal relationships between the development of airstrips and the subsequent local deforestation.

Figure 3 NDVI Landsat imagery displayed for point ID: 508 before and after airstrip development. a) 2010 and b) 2014.

4. Conclusion:

Understanding the implications of airstrip development, and providing a means for their detection, can help support environmental strategies and initiatives, such as the Action Plan for the Prevention and Control of Deforestation in the Legal Amazon (PPCDAm). Further research in this area might consider expanding to other protected areas, or to other transportation systems such as roads and logging tracks to further understand their direct impact on the surrounding environment. Strengthening this research and relating initiatives can help enhance law enforcement and improve policy frameworks to better tackle deforestation issues.

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Biographies

Kate A. Booth is a GIS analyst and post-graduate researcher focusing on the use of GIS and Remote Sensing to monitor deforestation in the Brazilian Amazon. She has a bachelor's degree in Ocean Exploration from the University of Plymouth, and an MSc in GIS from the University of Manchester.

Jonathan J. Huck is Professor of Computational Geography at the University of Manchester.

Polyanna da Conceição Bispo is a Senior Lecturer in Physical Geography at the University of Manchester.